

European topics in the electoral platforms of the Romanian political parties. Congruencies, discrepancies, future political directions

Alina Carmen Brihan¹ and Laurențiu Petrila²

Abstract

This paper aims to qualitatively analyze the electoral platforms of the seven Romanian parties that exceeded the 5% electoral threshold, in both the European Parliament and the Romanian Parliament elections, in 2024. These are the four pro-European parties (PSD, PNL, USR, UDMR) and three populist parties (AUR, SOS - Partidul SOS România, and POT). The objectives of the paper are, therefore, to identify the extent to which the approach to the European issues in the political programs of the aforementioned parties reflects both the ideology of the party and the ideological orientation of the political group to which they belong in the European Parliament; the degree to which these political parties understand the obligations that Romania's membership entails in the multilevel governance of the EU, but also the danger that ignoring these obligations may pose to democracy at national and European level.

Keywords

Multilevel governance; European elections; parliamentary elections; political parties; public policies

¹ Alina Carmen Brihan (ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0714-6988>) is a Lecturer at the Department of Political Science and Communication Sciences, University of Oradea. With BA degrees in Political Science ("Babeș-Bolyai" University, Cluj-Napoca) and in Law (University of Oradea), with MA specializations in European Studies (University of Reims, France) and International Relations ("Babeș-Bolyai" University), and a PhD and a postdoctoral fellowship in History (University of Oradea), she has channeled scientific research interests towards areas such as: European governance, EU decision-making, and active European citizenship. Email: alina_brihan@yahoo.com.

² Laurențiu Petrila (ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8415-3327>) is a Lecturer at the University of Oradea, in the Department of International Relations and European Studies. He earned a PhD in International Relations and European Studies from Babeș-Bolyai University in Cluj-Napoca and a PhD in Public Theology from Aurel Vlaicu University of Arad. He also completed a postdoctoral fellowship in Sociology at the University of Oradea. He has undertaken several research fellowships at the University of Vienna, Charles University in Prague, and the European University Institute in Florence. His research interests include cultural and social anthropology, societal security, and social evolution and transformation from the perspectives of migration, culture, and causal extremism. E-mail: laurentiu.petrila@didactic.oradea.ro.

Introduction

Romania's "coming of age" as a member state of the European Union (EU) on January 1, 2025, has found Romania facing a "first" in its post-1989 democratic electoral history, namely the resumption of presidential elections – on May 4, 2025 (first round) and May 18, 2025 (second round), and, implicitly, the extension of the 2024 electoral year, which initially provided for four rounds of elections: June 9, 2024 - local elections and elections for the European Parliament (start date of the election campaign - May 10, 2024); November 24, 2024 - presidential elections, first round, canceled by the decision of the Constitutional Court of Romania; December 1, 2024 - parliamentary elections (start date of the election campaign - November 1, 2024); December 8, 2024 - presidential elections, second round - canceled.

At the juncture between the local, European Parliament, and parliamentary elections, which were completed in 2024, and the presidential elections, which were to be resumed in 2025, on January 1, 2025, when Romania celebrated both 18 years of EU membership and full integration into the Schengen area, by eliminating land border controls, Romania found itself in the midst of intense internal turmoil regarding the path it would follow, at the executive level (president, government), in its foreign policy: would it maintain the European path, or would it deviate towards the East?

The results of the European Parliament and local elections on June 9, 2024, brought a victory for pro-European political forces, while the parliamentary elections held six months later, on December 1, 2024, ended with over 55% of the votes going to pro-European parties, but with a populist party in second place (AUR - Alliance for the Union of Romanians) in terms of number of votes, and two other populist parties (SOS - SOS Romania Party and POT - Young People's Party) in fifth and sixth place out of the seven parties that exceeded the 5% electoral threshold and entered the Romanian Parliament for the 2024-2028 term (the pro-European parties are: PSD - Social Democratic Party, PNL - National Liberal Party, USR - Save Romania Union, UDMR - Hungarian Democratic Union of Romania). Therefore, the stakes of the May 2025 presidential election were extremely high, not only from the perspective of the future president-elect or the future government of Romania, but also from the perspective of the path that Romania will take, both externally and internally. The success of the pro-European candidate for the Romanian presidency, Nicușor Dan, led to the creation of a pro-European governing coalition, and the installation of a government for the 2025-2028 term, consisting of PSD, PNL, UDMR, and the national minorities.

On the other hand, although European elections are generally considered "second-tier elections" (Reif and Schmitt, 1980), with citizens giving greater weight to national elections than European ones, in the 2024 European Parliament and local elections in Romania, voter turnout for the election of Romania's representatives to the European Parliament was 52.40%, while for the election of mayors and county council presidents it was 49.62% and 50.55% respectively, and for the parliamentary elections it was 52.50%, a figure comparable to that for the European Parliament elections.

In the European elections of June 6-9, 2024, European citizens elected 720 members of the European Parliament from approximately 18,400 candidates, with Romania being represented by 33 MEPs. Thus, for the 2024-2029 term, eight political groups (EPP, S&D, ECR, Renew Europe, PEF, Greens/EFA, GUE/NGL, ENS), plus 32 non-attached members, will be active in the European Parliament. As for Romania, of the 33 MEPs, six far-right populist MEPs (from the AUR party) are part of the CRE group, and two MEPs (from the SOS Romania party) are unaffiliated, with the remaining 25 Romanian MEPs joining the EPP, S&D, Renew Europe, and Greens/EFA groups (Nicolae Ștefănuță – independent candidate).

The October 2024 report by the European Center for Populist Studies (ECPS) (Ivaldi and Zankina, 2024: 396-428) examined the electoral performance and influence of the populist parties in the 2024 European elections. According to the report, the results of the 2024 European elections confirmed the electoral consolidation of the populist phenomenon in Europe, with these parties winning 263 of the 720 seats, representing approximately 36%. The causes of the rise in popularity of populist movements in Europe can be found, according to the Report, in the various crises to which EU citizens have been exposed over the last 17 years, namely the 2008 financial crisis, the 2015 refugee crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic, and now the wars in Ukraine and Gaza. Right-wing populists (who won 177 seats, or 24%) are currently divided into three different groups - namely the ECR (78 members, including the six MEPs from the AUR party), the P/E (49 members), and the ESN (25 members), but populist parties are also found among non-affiliated MEPs (as is the case of SOS Romania Party).

At the EU level, 2024 marked a new term of office not only for the European Parliament but also for the European Commission. While the previous European Commission (2019-2024), led by Ursula von der Leyen, set six ambitious priorities (a European Green Deal, an economy at the service of citizens, a Europe fit for the digital age, protecting the European way of life, a stronger Europe in the world, and a new lease of life for European democracy), the new Commission - led by the same Ursula von der Leyen - has set seven priorities for the European Commission's 2024-2029 term (a new plan for Europe's sustainable prosperity and competitiveness; a new era for European defense and security; supporting citizens, strengthening our societies and the EU social model; maintaining the quality of life of EU citizens: food security, water, and nature; protecting democracy and defending EU values; Europe in the world: leveraging the EU's strength and partnerships; achieving our goals together and preparing the EU for the future), priorities that build on the European Council's EU Strategic Agenda and discussions with political groups in the European Parliament.

The Strategic Agenda for 2024-2029 (drawn up by EU leaders in June 2024), in the context of the European Parliament elections and ahead of the appointment of the new European Commission, sets out three priority areas to guide the work of the EU institutions over the next five years: a free and democratic Europe (promoting and protecting the rule of law; strengthening resilience and democratic debate; protecting free and pluralistic media and civil society; combating foreign interference and attempts at destabilization, etc.); a strong and secure Europe (continuing support for Ukraine, including its reconstruction, and pursuing a just peace; greater EU defense preparedness and capacity, and increased defense spending and investment; cooperation with transatlantic partners and NATO; combating organized crime, radicalization, terrorism, and violent extremism; strengthening resilience, preparedness, crisis prevention, and response capabilities; an EU enlargement process based on merit, with incentives, to be carried out in parallel with the necessary internal reforms; a comprehensive approach to migration and border management); a prosperous and competitive Europe (a deeper single market, in particular for energy, finance and telecommunications; an ambitious, robust, open and sustainable trade policy; reducing harmful dependencies and diversifying and securing strategic supply chains; improving capacity in key technologies of the future; the green and digital transitions; a sustainable and resilient agricultural sector; promoting an innovation- and business-friendly environment; strengthening cooperation in the field of health at European and international level; investing in skills, training, and education).

Consequently, the issues that the European Commission will focus on within the seven priorities for the 2024-2029 term are: facilitating the stimulation of economic growth by businesses; supporting competitive EU industries and creating quality jobs; developing a circular and resilient economy that puts research and innovation at its heart and accelerates investment; addressing skills

and labor shortages; and stimulating innovation in digital technology (priority 1); ensuring greater safety and security for European citizens by building a European Defense Union, addressing all online and offline threats, and preparing to counter crises; strengthening common borders and managing migration in a fair and firm manner (priority 2); supporting and improving the quality of life of European citizens by promoting social fairness in the modern economy; strengthening solidarity between citizens by bringing EU societies together and supporting young people, as well as ensuring equal opportunities for all (priority 3); building a competitive and resilient agricultural and food system and protecting biodiversity to support European farmers and benefit from healthy food; adapting to and preparing for a changing climate (priority 4); protecting and defending democracy and increasing the resilience of European societies; strengthening the rule of law for a fair and functioning society; promoting civic engagement and participation to bring citizens' ideas to the heart of policy-making (priority 5); expanding the EU to increase its influence on the world stage; focusing on the wider neighborhood to promote peace, partnerships, and economic stability; pursuing a new external economic policy and reforming the international system to adapt it to today's world (priority 6); Developing a simpler and more impactful EU budget to deliver funds where they matter most; implementing reforms to ensure the smooth functioning of an enlarged Union and strengthening the partnership between the European Commission and the European Parliament so that objectives can be achieved more effectively (priority 7).

After five difficult years for European societies and their citizens, and equally for the EU, due to the long series of challenges they have faced – from the COVID-19 pandemic, Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine, the energy crisis, the fight against climate change, and the situation in the Middle East – but also in the context of the EU's efforts to address them (such as providing resources for Europe's recovery through a new instrument, NextGenerationEU; providing humanitarian, financial, and military assistance to Ukraine; the adoption of 13 packages of sanctions against Russia; the strengthening of the partnership with NATO; the creation of REPowerEU to ensure energy supply and reduce dependence on Russia; the European Green Deal; and taking concrete measures to promote free and fair elections, strengthen media freedom, and combat disinformation), it is important to analyze the impact of challenges and transformations, whether negative or positive, at the European level on Romanian citizens' perceptions of life, their fears and expectations both at home and at EU level, as well as on European and national policies and institutions.

In the context of the end of the European Commission's 2019-2024 mandate, a survey of EU citizens' opinions on its priorities showed that the areas in which the EU should act in the medium term are security and defense (32%), jobs (31%), and health (28%). Looking ahead, the idea of a common foreign policy for EU Member States is supported by 64% of Romanians, 60% are in favor of a common trade policy, and 58% are in favor of EU enlargement (European Commission, 2024a).

Ahead of the European elections in June 2024, European institutions are known to an above-average extent, with 78% of Romanians having heard of the European Parliament (and 57% trusting it), 75% of the European Commission (which enjoys a 55% trust rating), and 74% have heard of the European Council (with 57% of respondents trusting this institution). Trust in the EU is also above average, with 58% of Romanians holding this view, and the EU's image among the Romanian public is positive - 46%. However, 53% of Romanians feel that their voice does not matter in the EU. Knowledge of how the EU works is affirmed by 64% of respondents, with 72% also stating that they are aware that the European Parliament is directly elected by the citizens of each Member State. The future of the EU is viewed with optimism by 66% of Romanians, with 52% sharing the opinion that more decisions should be taken at EU level (European Commission, 2024b).

When it comes to economic issues, 63% of Romanians are satisfied with their current lifestyle, but they are pessimistic (31%) about their lives in the next 12 months. Rising prices, inflation, and the cost of living are the main concerns, both personally and nationally, for Romanian citizens (47% and 43%, respectively), followed by their household's financial situation, personally (18%), and the economic situation, nationally (27%). At the European level, however, Russia's invasion of Ukraine (31%) and the international situation (20%) are the main concerns. As for the direction things are heading in Romania (57%) and the EU (49%), it is considered to be the wrong one. In the context of these dissatisfactions, it is not surprising that Romanian public opinion lacks confidence in domestic political structures: in political parties (73%), in parliament (66%), in the government (65%), while local public authorities are the only institutions in which 49% of respondents have confidence. Similarly, 54% of Romanians are dissatisfied with the way democracy works in Romania (European Commission, 2024b).

More than 50% of Europeans are only occasionally interested in political issues at the national, local, and European levels, an attitude that is also shared by Romanian citizens with regard to, for example, political issues at the European level (54%). However, 57% of Romanian respondents believe that their country's interests are adequately taken into account in the EU. When asked to choose the terms that best define the EU, Romanian respondents ranked them as follows: it is modern (74%), democratic (71%), forward-looking (70%), responds quickly in crisis situations (66%), efficient (64%), protective (64%), united (61%), bureaucratic (58%), or distant (46%) (European Commission, 2024b).

The paper therefore aims to analyze the European themes included in the electoral programs of Romanian political parties that reached the electoral threshold, both in the European elections on June 9 and in the parliamentary elections on December 1, in the 2024 election year. Thus, four pro-European parties (PSD - Social Democratic Party, PNL - National Liberal Party, USR - Save Romania Union, UDMR - Hungarian Democratic Union of Romania) and three populist parties (AUR - Alliance for the Union of Romanians, SOS - SOS Romania Party, and POT - Young People's Party).

The arguments underlying the choice for European and parliamentary elections are as follows: in the same year, elections for the two legislative institutions at national level (elections for the Romanian Parliament are held every four years) and European level (elections for the European Parliament are held every five years), directly elected by citizens, overlapped; and, at the same time, both institutions faced uncertainties in 2024 regarding the balance of pro-European versus populist forces that would result from the elections. For this reason, the stakes in these elections were extremely high for all parties in the electoral race, especially for those considered to have more or less visible chances (see the case of populist parties) of entering the two legislative structures. Also, the percentages and number of seats obtained by the parties that would pass the electoral threshold in the two institutions are important both nationally and at the European level, as follows: in the first case, because of the coalitions they can form to establish a new government and, implicitly, because of the domestic and foreign policy directions that this new government would follow; and at the European level, due to the influence that political groups can have on the formulation of European policies and, subsequently, on national policies, as a result of the legislative transposition process.

As regards the option of identifying European issues in the electoral offers of political parties, this is linked to the interest in seeing: whether the frameworks used by political parties on these issues reflect the ideology of the party and the political group to which they belong in the European Parliament; whether the approach to European values, objectives, and policies demonstrates an understanding of the role that a Member State has in promoting both the national and European interests of the state in the European decision-making process and in the formulation of European

policies, but also an understanding of the obligations that EU membership entails; what is the difference between the approach of pro-European parties and that of populist parties, which are on the rise at both European and national level; whether and how the European Commission's priorities, based on the European Council's Strategic Agenda for the EU (agreed by EU leaders) and on discussions with political groups in the European Parliament, are reflected in the priorities of the political groups and in the governing program of the new Romanian government; or whether the concerns of Romanian citizens regarding national or European politics are adequately addressed in the electoral offers of the political parties in the two rounds of elections under analysis.

Presentation of the EU's multilevel governance framework, from a theoretical and EU law perspective, through the prism of values, objectives, priorities, policies, relations between actors and decision-making levels, or the influence of the government on the formation of public opinion, is a necessary step for understanding the strategies used by political parties in designing their electoral offers for the 2024 European Parliament and parliamentary elections in Romania, but also for identifying the degree of convergence or divergence that exists between the values and priorities of the EU and those of the Romanian political parties that won the two types of elections mentioned above.

Representative democracy at national and European level and the current challenges to multilevel governance in the EU

For Romania and, implicitly, for each of the 27 Member States of the EU, membership of this *sui generis* regional organization (Hix, 1998; Bărbulescu, 2015) also concerns the more or less effective way in which each state (the actors and decision-making levels that comprise it) positions itself within the EU's multilevel governance. The Treaty of Lisbon represented an important step forward in strengthening multilevel governance, through the way it addressed relations between the Union and Member States down to regional and local level, but also the Union's obligations towards Member States and those of the latter towards the Union. Thus, the Union's political obligations towards Member States are as follows: equality of all Member States, a provision aimed at allaying the fears of small and medium-sized states regarding the possible domination of large states; respect for national identity, political and constitutional structures, but also local and regional autonomy; to respect and assist Member States in achieving the objectives of the Treaties. With regard to the obligations of Member States towards the Union, in accordance with the principle of loyal cooperation, Member States are required to respect and assist the Union in fulfilling the tasks set out in the Treaties; to take measures to ensure the fulfillment of obligations arising from the Treaties or resulting from the acts of the Union institutions; and, last but not least, to refrain from any measure that could jeopardize the attainment of the Union's objectives.

Although the Treaty presented these relationships through an explicit set of rules, so that citizens would be aware of the responsibilities of actors at different political levels (local, regional, national, European), we believe that the way in which these relationships, as well as the role of each decision-making level in the European decision-making process and in the formulation of European public policies, are "translated" to citizens by national political actors is influenced by their pro-European versus populist stance.

The Treaty of Lisbon therefore attempts to define and explain the European political model to citizens by bringing together in one place the values (respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law, and respect for human rights) and objectives of the EU; stipulating that respect for EU values is common to Member States and is a mandatory condition for states wishing to

become members of the EU; clarifying the relationship between the EU and Member States, as mentioned above; declaring that the principles of representative democracy and participatory democracy occupy an important place within the EU; but also strengthening the role of national parliaments in the European decision-making process.

Therefore, the criteria for EU governance are considered by some authors to be *the Copenhagen Criteria* (1993), covering distinct dimensions of governance. Of the three categories of criteria, the political criteria and those relating to the state's ability to assume the obligations of membership, which derive from EU law and policies, aim to ensure: commitment to democracy – this is a condition for the EU's assessment of a state's application for membership; adherence to the rule of law – fundamental to democracy and governance; respect for human and minority rights; administrative efficiency – important for the use of EU funds and the implementation of EU regulations and directives; acceptance of the *acquis communautaire*; or the administrative capacity of governments to implement the *acquis* (as they are the ones that administer the directives and regulations).

Theorists of multilevel governance have addressed issues such as the following over the past 40 years: affirming the unique character of the EU's multilevel governance (Marks, Hooghe, and Blank, 1996: 341-378); the fact that governance beyond the state does not necessarily mean governance above the state, and the fact that the EU is not a reproduction of the processes and policies that previously formed the nation state (Schmitter, 1996), but rather a network of national and supranational regulatory institutions, held together by shared values and a common decision-making process (Majone, 1996: 217); the fact that the EU's multilevel governance involves the interconnection, in a permanently negotiated manner, of international, national, and subnational governance processes; but also that multilevel governance is based on the increasing recognition of multiple types of actors and multiple decision-making levels in the decision-making process, and on the multiplication of the number and types of decision-making networks through which actors interact (Ion, 2013: 111-112; Lange et al., 2013: 404).

Although national actors are considered to be the most important actors in the European decision-making process, decision-making powers are divided between actors at the national, supranational, and subnational levels; which, according to some authors, leads to an increasingly significant role for supranational actors, who in some cases exert greater influence on the European decision-making process than nation states. Multilevel governance also provides support in understanding the context in which powers are transferred "upwards" to supranational organizations, laterally to quasi-autonomous actors, and "down" to sub-national authorities, but also in illustrating the relationships within and between different levels of government and governance through the principle of partnership (Potluka and Liddle, 2014: 1436).

From the perspective of the "new governance" theory, Simon Hix states that, given that the decision-making process in the EU is not the same as that in the nation state, the process – from initiation to adoption and implementation – is complex and involves constant cooperation and deliberation between the different levels (Hix, 1998: 39).

In his analysis of the European political model, Professor Iordan Gheorghe Bărbulescu states that, in the EU, member states remain the guarantors of multilevel sovereignty, which is, on the one hand, common and European, and, on the other hand, is national (Bărbulescu, 2015: 345-346, 437). Thus, within the framework of EU multilevel governance, we observe a shift in approach from government (associated with governance - the formal institutions of the state) to a new, European form of governance, which assumes that hierarchical forms of government have given way to non-

hierarchical forms of governance, thereby achieving a transition from state-centered governance to society-centered governance. In view of this, Romania's integration into the EU also represented its accession to a supranational, European set of public policies. Borrás and Radaelli stated that, in comparison with the architecture of governance and public policy programs, in which, on a continuum of abstraction, multilevel governance is at the highest level (Borrás and Radaelli, 2011: 468-469).

The concept of "Europeanization", although it does not yet have a unified approach in the literature, essentially refers to the impact of European policy and policies on Member States, but also to the redefinition by Member States of their interests and behavior in accordance with the norms, challenges, and logic of EU membership (Auel, 2005: 305). Europeanization has also been defined as the process by which areas of national policy have become subjects of European decision-making, but also as a process of national adaptation to the pressures resulting, directly or indirectly, from EU membership. These definitions show that Europeanization is the independent variable and changes at the national level are the dependent variable (Auel, 2005: 305).

In the EU's multilevel governance, the process of formulating European policies is also considered to be a multilevel one (European, national, regional, local), involving interaction between various public and private actors. However, the impact of European policies at the national level depends on the institutional compatibility between European policy requirements and national administrative arrangements (Knill, 2003: 42).

In this process, internal actors are not passive recipients of EU institutions and policies; the adoption and adaptation of EU norms, rules, and models into internal structures - national or regional - involves, for the most part, active processes of interpretation, incorporation of new norms and rules into existing institutions, but also resistance to certain rules and regulations. Therefore, the internal processes of Member States are active processes of adaptation, change, interpretation, and resistance. Furthermore, the way in which internal change processes are carried out also depends on several conditions, such as: national incentives; the extent to which states are able to adopt and implement decisions; or the democratic quality of the state - which influences the willingness of national actors to promote internal change in response to EU influence (Borrás and Radaelli, 2011: 8-13).

The conceptualization of Europeanisation in the literature has focused on several aspects, including: the increase in the powers and authority of actors and institutions at EU level (the link between Europeanisation and European integration is explicit, Europeanization being the explicit manifestation of political integration - embodied in the institutions and governance structures of the EU; the mechanism of procedural change is the effect of coordination between multiple actors, organizations, and institutions; the basic procedural mode is given by the socialization of elites) (Olsen, 2002: 921-952); the impact of supranational authority and increased powers in terms of politics, policies, and nation states (it is considered that there is a direct link between Europeanization and European integration; Europeanization - as a national impact - results from a top-down political integration process and involves the "downloading" of policy paradigms, programs, and mechanisms from the EU level to the national levels; the mechanism of procedural change is provided by economic and political integration - which involves coordination between multiple actors, organizations, and institutions; and the basic procedural mode is defined by the legitimization of technocratic discourse) (Adshead, 2005: 159-178; Goldsmith, 2003: 112-133).

Article 13 of the Treaty on EU states that "the EU has an institutional framework designed to promote its values, pursue its objectives, and support its interests, the effectiveness and continuity of its policies and actions. (...) Each institution shall act within the limits of the powers conferred on it by the Treaties, in accordance with the procedures, conditions and objectives laid down therein. The

institutions shall cooperate in a spirit of loyalty." Consequently, it can be considered that we have a common institutional system specific to the Union, which articulates and makes functional the institutions through which common policies are implemented, and EU objectives are achieved within the limits of action established by the treaties.

Under the Treaty of Lisbon, national parliaments acquire more rights and powers, such as: receiving information, draft legislative and non-legislative acts directly from the institutions of the EU; verifying compliance with the principle of subsidiarity; participating in the procedures for revising the treaties (Article 48 TEU); being informed about applications for accession to the Union (Article 49 TEU); participating in interparliamentary cooperation between national parliaments and with the European Parliament (Protocol on the role of national parliaments in the EU). National parliaments also receive, among other things: the Commission's consultation documents (green papers, white papers, communications); the European Commission's annual legislative program; any legislative programming or policy strategy instrument; draft legislative acts and amended drafts; the agenda and results of Council meetings; European Council initiatives to activate "passerelle" clauses, etc. Thus, national parliaments are called upon to act as "guardians" of national competences in the face of possible abuse by European institutions.

Consequently, if the executives of all 27 Member States deliberate together on issues that were previously decided only at national level, it is the national parliaments that transpose EU decisions into national law, the national courts interpret EU law, and subnational regions implement EU regulations (Schmidt, 2006: 1-2). In approaching the EU decision-making process, *agenda-setting* is also important, although research on EU governance has paid little attention to it (Peters, 2001: 77–94; Tallberg, 2003: 1–19). Thus, the *agenda-setting* process at the EU level contributes not only to understanding the European decision-making process, but also to highlighting structural trends in European decision-making, or even to understanding the development of European integration in general, the level of European integration, and the issues addressed by the EU (Princen, 2007: 21-22). However, *agenda-setting* models at the national level have institutional and political characteristics similar to the *agenda-setting* process at the EU level. Thus, at the national level, the "agenda" represents a set of issues that are taken most seriously (Tallberg, 2003: 5). Thus, in a state, several types of agendas can be identified: the political agenda (issues considered by decision-makers); the public agenda (issues considered important by the public and identified through opinion polls); and the media agenda (issues covered by the mass media). These agendas do not necessarily overlap, so attention must be paid to the degree and manner in which these agendas influence each other. At EU level, however, each institution has its own agenda, and these differences between agendas are essential for the analysis of *agenda-setting* in the EU; likewise, perspectives derived from national political systems on *agenda-setting* need to be modified to fit the specific institutional characteristics of the EU (Princen, 2007: 28-29).

With regard to the first level of the European public policy-making process, namely that concerning the relationship between the EU institutions and the Member States, the powers of the European institutions are those established by the founding treaties and are aimed at achieving the objectives of the Communities and the Union. Any extension of powers therefore requires a revision of the treaties. Thus, in some areas, powers are more extensive, and in others, they are more limited; in some areas, they belong solely to the Communities, in others, solely to the Member States, although the harmonization of Member States' national legislation limits, to a certain extent, the scope for action at national level, while in others, they are shared. However, the Community's powers must comply with both the principle of proportionality and that of subsidiarity.

According to the Treaty of Lisbon, the Union's powers fall into three categories: exclusive powers (customs union; establishing competition rules necessary for the functioning of the internal market; monetary policy for Member States whose currency is the euro; conservation of marine biological resources under the common fisheries policy; common commercial policy; the conclusion of an international agreement where such conclusion is provided for in a Union legislative act, or is necessary to enable the Union to exercise its internal competence, or insofar as it could affect common rules or alter their scope); shared competences with the Member States in specific areas, where both the Union and the Member States may legislate and adopt legally binding acts, without these competences overlapping (internal market; social policy, for the aspects defined in this Treaty; economic, social and territorial cohesion; agriculture and fisheries, except for the conservation of marine biological resources; the environment; consumer protection; transport; trans-European networks; energy; the area of freedom, security and justice; common security objectives in the field of public health, for the aspects defined in this Treaty); and competences to support, coordinate or complement the action of Member States, without thereby replacing the competences of the States in the areas concerned (protection and improvement of human health; industry; culture; tourism; education, vocational training, youth and sport; civil protection; administrative cooperation).

The way in which competences are exercised in the relationship between the European and national levels of each Member State is determined by EU law, the relationship between European legislation and that of the Member States, and the way in which the European institutions are organized and function, their powers in the European decision-making process and in the formulation of European public policies.

Preparing at the national level for the development of European policies is therefore an extremely important test for national governments; they must represent their interests in various areas (Metcalfe, 2008: 104). This involves internal challenges related to various circumstances and requirements, including constitutional ones, but also to the distribution of governmental power. The creation of a system for representing national interests at European level is a constructed one and depends on the overall system of internal policy coordination. Governments enjoy a high degree of freedom of action through which they can exert influence over European-level decisions for their own benefit. The way in which states coordinate at European level, the way in which European policies are formulated, but also the strategies and tactics used in Brussels, are also a reflection of the image that each state wishes to project.

In the context of European governance, Lord and Magnette analyzed the relationship between legitimacy and democracy through the lens of four "vectors of legitimacy": indirect legitimacy (legitimacy transferred from the national level to EU institutions); parliamentary legitimacy (concerns the influencing and control functions of national parliaments and the European Parliament in the European decision-making process); technocratic legitimacy (assessed by the ability of EU institutions to resolve complex and technically difficult problems efficiently and effectively in the interests of citizens); and procedural legitimacy (resulting from the decision-making process, i.e. how actors or institutions coordinate to make collective decisions) (Lord and Magnette, 2004: 183-202).

If, at the national level, legitimacy is defined as a particular motivation for accepting political governance and is rooted in citizens' affiliation with a set of fundamental values and their structural realization within the rights, institutions, and processes of the state (Bolleyer and Reh, 2012: 473), at the supranational level of the EU, Hurrelmann and DeBardeleben believe that legitimacy must represent the multilevel character of the EU, as well as the interaction between national and supranational politics (Hurrelmann and DeBardeleben, 2009: 229-247). Thus, national interests have

become part of a European decision-making process involving many actors in a complex set of interactions, with multiple channels of access (Decker, 2002: 258).

In other words, in the representative democracies of the EU, understanding public attitudes is important because public opinion is a means of connecting citizens and elected officials. On the one hand, public opinion is how the public is seen as having a certain ability to control those who govern. On the other hand, those who govern can influence the process of shaping public opinion, the content of citizens' opinions and attitudes. This cyclical process influences the type and manner of political debates that take place in the public sphere (Scotto and Singer, 2004).

As for how those in power influence public opinion, it is important to analyze the "frames" (Druckman, 2001: 226–231) they use in their public discourse. In this sense, the "frame" is shaped by the constructions and definitions that governments give to social problems or solutions to a particular public policy. This is because governments know that if their frame becomes the dominant way of thinking about a particular issue, then they have won the battle for public opinion. There is also competition between parties that produce alternative frames on the same issue, just as there is competition in the interpretation of frames by public opinion. Thus, "frames" become alternative descriptions or interpretations of the same information, problems, or solutions. They guide understanding of the origins of a problem, and public policies can be framed in such a way as to emphasize a narrow part of a broader problem, with the effect (intended or not) that the recipient's judgments and opinions are governed by those ideas and not others. Not surprisingly, citizens favor the facts, values and ideas that have been brought to their attention through frames (Nelson, 2004: 4).

According to various studies on the effects of "frames," they either represent the imposition of "frames" by those in power or are seen as the result of both the content of the message and the knowledge and predispositions of the recipient. Successful "frames" must first and foremost consider the existing values of the target audience and emphasize the special importance of a particular value in a particular issue, rather than infiltrating the audience with a totally new value structure (Nelson, 2004: 6). "Frames" affect the receiver's objective on a particular issue, and personal priorities affect opinions on a particular policy. Individuals select those messages that confirm their political orientation.

The analysis of "frames" becomes even more important when comparing the "frames" produced by traditional parties versus populist parties, which are reflected in the electoral support they receive from the population. In the European political landscape, populist political parties (Ivaldi and Zankina, 2024: 16-33) can be found on both the left and right of the European political spectrum, as well as in the center. Populism "views society as ultimately divided into two homogeneous and antagonistic groups, 'the pure people' versus 'the corrupt elite'," and manifests a general distrust of traditional political institutions and a growing polarization of society. It is fueled by a complex interaction of socioeconomic, cultural, and political factors, and is often Eurosceptic.

As mentioned in the beginning, democracy is one of the fundamental values of the EU, seen as a supranational organization, but also of each Member State or candidate country. And in a democracy, both political pluralism and pluralistic, open contestation, within accepted rules of the game that are then transmitted through free and fair elections to the central political system, are part of how it works. However, when the rules of the democratic game are broken and democracy is under attack, it is imperative to raise awareness of this situation and mobilize voters to preserve the democratic status quo. The year 2024 found Romania grappling with such a challenge, more so in relation to the presidential, parliamentary, and European elections than the local ones. Therefore, we aim to conduct a qualitative analysis of the electoral offers of the seven parties that cleared the

electoral threshold in both the European Parliament and Romanian Parliament elections. For each party, we analyze the electoral program for the elections for Romania's representatives in the European Parliament, the priorities of the European political group to which the political party belongs, the party's governing program for the parliamentary elections, and the degree of compatibility between the governing program of the respective party and that of the European political group to which it belongs.

Consequently, we propose three hypotheses in this paper. Hypothesis 1: The frameworks used by political parties in their electoral programs, on European issues, reflect both the ideology of the party and the ideological orientation of the political group to which they belong in the European Parliament. Hypothesis 2: The presence of European issues in the electoral programs of political parties reflects an understanding of the role that a Member State has in the multilevel governance of the EU, that of promoting both the national and European interests of the state in the European decision-making process and in the formulation of European policies. Hypothesis 3: Political parties that, in addressing European issues, do not support the values, objectives, and priorities of the EU, demonstrate a lack of responsibility in fulfilling the obligations of EU membership under the treaties, which may affect the quality of democracy at both the national and European levels.

National and European issues on the political agendas of the pro-European majority

This section aims to analyze the electoral offers of the four pro-European political parties (PSD, PNL, USR, UDMR), which passed the 5% electoral threshold to secure seats in the European Parliament and the Romanian Parliament and which, at the domestic level, managed to lay the foundations for the new pro-European governing coalition for the 2025-2028 term.

The **Social Democratic Party (PSD)**. The Social Democratic Party (PSD) is a center-left party. It is the successor to the National Salvation Front (FSN), which later became the Democratic Front for National Salvation (FDSN) in 1992, and then the Party of Social Democracy in Romania (PDSR) – since 1993, the PSD (formed in 2001 through the merger of the PDSR and the PSDR) considers itself the successor to the more than 130-year-old historical tradition of Romanian social democracy³. For the PSD, democracy is a prerequisite for a prosperous society, equality is a fundamental principle of democracy, justice is a guarantor of a democratic society, and human rights are at the heart of the political and public agenda⁴, values that are in line with those defined by the EU in Article 2 of the Treaty of Lisbon. At the same time, PSD defines itself as "the most pro-European party in Romania" and "wants a social Europe, a fair and cohesive EU"⁵. During the PSD government (2000-2004), Romania joined NATO and began the process of integration into the EU.

Over the past 35 years, PSD has governed alone or supported the government during several periods, and the 2024 election year found the party in power, but in a complicated situation. Since 2021, PSD has been in government alongside PNL and UDMR (the latter only until 2023) within the National Coalition for Romania (CNR). Since 2023, PSD has been in government alongside PNL in a bipartisan CNR formula, but after the local and European elections in June 2024, the president of the National Liberal Party (PNL), Nicolae Ciucă, declared on October 7, 2024, that the party he leads is ending its coalition with the Social Democratic Party (PSD), but remains in government (Onofrei, 2024). In the nine rounds of parliamentary elections from 1990 to the 2024 elections, the PSD - alone or in

³ See the official website of the party at: <https://www.psd.ro/proiecte/130-ani-de-social-democratie/>.

⁴ See <https://www.psd.ro/valorile-noastre/>.

⁵ See <https://www.psd.ro/directia-noastra-politica/>.

alliances - had the largest number of MPs in both the Chamber of Deputies and the Senate, except for the 1996 and 2008 elections.

As regards the membership of Romanian political parties in the political groups in the European Parliament, PSD has been a full member of the Party of European Socialists (PES) since May 19, 2005, a political group that became S&D (Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats) in 2009. In the four rounds of elections for Romania's representatives in the European Parliament, held until the 2024 elections, PSD, alone or in alliance, had the largest number of MEPs in the 2009 and 2014 European elections, while in the 2007 and 2019 elections, it came second.

The European Parliament elections held on June 9, 2024 in Romania generated, for the first time at this level and in the context in which PSD and PNL are part of different political groups in the European Parliament, an alliance between the two parties and a merger of the European Parliament elections with the local elections. This was justified by prime minister Ciolacu, by the danger of the extremist wave and the path that Romania will follow in the future, namely achieving the objective of full integration into the Schengen area and integration into the OECD (Vulpe, 2024). Emergency Ordinance 21 of March 8, 2024, offers additional arguments for the Government's decision to combine the elections: ensuring greater representation of Romanian members in the European Parliament and strengthening Romania's position in the EU by sending a clear signal that it wishes to pursue a pro-EU stance and projects for the development of the Union down to the smallest administrative-territorial units.

The decision to combine the European Parliament elections with the local elections was supported by UDMR (its president, Kelemen Hunor, stating "there is nothing undemocratic about this combination", only that "it would have been better to announce it in advance, not at the last minute"), but it received a negative reaction from the opposition. The United Right Alliance (a center-right alliance including the Save Romania Union - USR, the People's Movement Party - PMP and the Right Force - FD, and established with the aim to participate in the 2024 elections) defined it as a move by which "the PSD and PNL are telling us that they want to steal the Romanian vote"⁶, while AUR representatives stated, in a similar tone, that the initiative to merge the elections is "just a political opportunity" for PNL and PSD to "eliminate competition" and claimed that the only ones who will lose from this merger are the leaders of the two parties, Nicolae Ciucă and Marcel Ciolacu.

On May 14, 2024, the Constitutional Court of Romania ruled unanimously that OUG 21/2024 is constitutional, both in terms of the justification of urgency and the use of OUG for legislation. However, the *Vot Corect* (Fair Vote) Coalition⁷ mentioned in the report it published after the European Parliament and local elections on June 9, 2024, that the decision to merge the elections should have been taken in Parliament, and not through an emergency ordinance, and recommended that "legislating through emergency ordinances to amend certain key aspects, political amendments that may benefit certain competitors, as well as amending electoral legislation shortly before elections, should be avoided". One effect of this merger, as stated in the Report, was that "the overlap of the two elections tended to highlight campaign issues related to local elections, and political activity focused on the competition for these elections" (Votcorect.ro, 2024).

⁶ <https://usr.ro/2024/02/21/dreapta-unita-va-avea-candidati-comuni-la-toate-alegerile-europarlamentare-locale-parlamentare-si-prezidentiale/>.

⁷ The coalition is made up of civic organizations working in the field of defending democracy and human rights and aims to monitor the process of organizing elections and referendums to ensure they are conducted according to constitutional principles, international standards and best practices to which Romania has adhered.

The alliance between the PSD and PNL for the European Parliament elections, an alliance between the two parties in power at the time of the June 9, 2024 elections, but members of two different political groups in the European Parliament, led to the development of a joint program, disseminated through the Alliance's campaign website, "stabilitate.ro", which became inaccessible after the European Parliament elections. In an Alliance flyer, under the slogan "We stand with Romania" and through five points, the two parties promise "stability and development". Thus, the five points⁸ present the advantages that voting for the PSD-PNL Alliance would bring to citizens, both domestically and externally, within the EU, with arguments being put forward to demonstrate that, through all its actions, the Alliance has proven, and can continue to prove in the future, that it "stands with Romania". On the one hand, regarding the domestic impact, the Alliance defines itself as the party that can bring stability, seriousness, balance, security, and, most importantly, development. Therefore, it would ensure the protection of citizens against the danger of extremism, external threats, but also against "potential representatives without experience and projects who only cause scandal". Bringing up the "facts" that speak for the Alliance, it is pointed out that the two parties have managed to increase the absorption rate of European funds from 25% to 96%, that they want to attract more European money into the country for reforms and investments (an objective that implicitly suggests the funds attracted through the PNRR), but also that they promote Romanian products and domestic capital in Europe. Looking ahead to the next term of Romanian MEPs, it is stated that the Alliance has experienced MEPs who know how to defend Romania's interests in Brussels; that, although the two parties have different doctrines and ideologies, they represent Romania in the European Parliament; and, last but not least, that together they are stronger and more influential in Brussels, with the PSD and PNL being part of the largest European political families, S&D and EPP.

Therefore, in the PSD-PNL Alliance Program⁹ we find a series of objectives aimed at placing Romania's development and modernization in a European context. Thus, from protecting Romanian capital (economy), supporting strategic industries, or stimulating innovation by doubling funds for research and innovation; to ensuring energy independence (energy) by using European funds and increasing renewable energy production and including energy investments among eligible expenses from European funds; to modernizing agriculture by accessing European funds and promoting Romanian products (agriculture); or to intensifying sanctions for environmental crimes; combating illegal waste trafficking; and allocating 30% of European funds to investments with an environmental component (environment), we note that the areas addressed in the electoral program include priorities that are in line with the European Commission's priorities for the 2019-2024 term. Full accession to the Schengen Area is considered a strategic priority, as the free movement of persons and goods contributes to economic growth and the consolidation of Romania's European integration. In this context, the diaspora is not forgotten either, with the PSD-PNL Alliance supporting measures to assist it, such as facilitating the acquisition of dual citizenship or digitizing public services to reduce bureaucracy. Last but not least, the electoral program makes a particular reference to the Republic of Moldova, based on the special nature of the bilateral relationship between the two countries, conferred by their shared language, history, culture, and traditions, but also on the European dimension of bilateral cooperation, based on the strategic objective of supporting the Republic of Moldova's integration into the EU, which is why the PSD-PNL Alliance affirms its support for Moldova on its path to EU accession.

⁸ See <https://romania.europalibera.org/a/alegeri-europarlamentare-promisiuni-candidati/32955009.html>.

⁹ Available at <https://www.stabilitate.ro>.

However, given that the Alliance's program was drawn up by two parties belonging to different European political families, any comparison between the PSD's electoral program and the priorities for the 2024-2029 term of the political group to which the PSD belongs can only be partial. The S&D group has stated that it will focus on the following areas during the new term of the European Parliament¹⁰: the social field (supporting initiatives to ensure a fair transition in the world of work, strengthening social dialogue and trade union rights, coordinating social security systems, creating a European social security card, revising the Temporary Agency Work Directive, paid and quality internships, a European anti-poverty strategy, a European strategy for older citizens, or social integration and access to quality jobs for people with disabilities), green and just transition (aiming to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 90–95% by 2040; strengthening the Green Deal, but with social support for vulnerable households and communities; updating the European Energy Security Strategy and placing energy efficiency, renewable energy, and clean technology production at its core; sustainable agricultural and rural policies, with protection for farmers and fair access to subsidies); European security and defense (building a European Defense Union, complementary to NATO; strengthening industrial defense capabilities; strong support for Ukraine), or support for EU enlargement (Western Balkans, Ukraine, Moldova, Georgia).

The directions presented above represent some of the 11 priorities of the S&D group in the European Parliament for the 2024-2029 term, and they also define the directions of future legislative requests addressed to the new European Commission. A comparison of the PSD's objectives with those of the S&D shows that the PSD is pursuing both national and European objectives, which will shape the actions of Romanian MEPs in the S&D group. In the European elections on June 6-9, 2024, citizens from the 27 EU member states sent 136 MEPs (out of a total of 720) to the S&D group, allowing the group to maintain its second position among the eight political groups in the European Parliament for the 2024-2029 term.

The first round of elections in Romania in 2024, namely the European Parliament and local elections on June 9, 2024, placed the PSD - PNL Alliance in first place among voters, with 48.55% in the European Parliament elections, at a turnout of 52.40%, namely 19 seats out of the 33 MEPs, of which the PSD has 11 MEPs. The PSD's leading position in the voters' choices was also maintained in the local elections, with the party obtaining 34.74% (with a turnout of 49.62%), or 1,677 seats, and 35.56% in the election of county council presidents, or 24 seats out of a total of 41.

The parliamentary elections on December 1, 2024, on the other hand, found the PSD and PNL as electoral competitors, according to the decisions taken by the two parties, but also as parties with interim presidents, following the resignation on November 25 of both PSD president Marcel Ciolacu and PNL president Nicolae Ciucă, following the failure of the two leaders in the first round of the presidential elections on November 24, 2024, when the former obtained 19.15% of the valid votes cast, and the latter 8.79%. For the parliamentary elections, the PSD's 2025-2028 government program, designed under the slogan "PSD - The Safe Path for Romania" includes, in addition to a chapter dedicated to the level of development Romania will reach after five years of PSD government, 16 chapters addressing various public policies¹¹. The objectives to be achieved in each policy area are constructed using precise figures, percentages, and deadlines, with the aim of giving weight and credibility to the promises made.

¹⁰ Available at: <https://www.socialistsanddemocrats.eu/ro/publications/sd-cererile-noastre-cheie-pentru-2024-2029>.

¹¹ Available at: https://www.psd.ro/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/Program_Guvernare_PSD_2025_2028.pdf.

However, the way in which European themes, policies, or funds are reflected in the PSD program can be analyzed with reference to the internal level on the one hand and the external level on the other. At the internal level, the aim is to attract European funds, in addition to using funds from the state budget, for the reindustrialization of Romania (by supporting various industrial sectors, investing in innovation and high technology in industry, developing and consolidating high-tech companies, and creating an investment fund for industrialization based on licenses and patents); digitization of public administration; labor and social solidarity (implementation of the European minimum wage; aid scheme to increase employment in areas with high unemployment, above 5%; integration of people with disabilities into the labor market and business environment; updating the skills or retraining of people affected by the just transition process); education (investment in educational infrastructure; expansion of the dual, vocational, and technical education program; strengthening of technological education); agriculture (modernization and expansion of irrigation systems; direct payments to equalize the subsidies received by Romanian farmers with those received by European farmers; support for Romanian vegetable, pork and chicken production; development of organic production; increase in the processing capacity of agricultural raw materials); environment (recycling and efficient waste management; investment in water supply and flood defense infrastructure; energy efficiency and clean energy); transport and infrastructure; SMEs and entrepreneurship (support for the creation of start-ups by Romanians returning from the diaspora and by students; the possibility for young people over the age of 18 to set up a "practice LLC"; support for young people entering agriculture); improving justice reforms based on the reports of European bodies (including the EC Report on the Rule of Law).

European funds represent a separate chapter among the 16 chapters of the PSD's proposed government program. Thus, one of the party's macroeconomic objectives is to achieve an absorption rate of 90% of EU funds for 2021-2027, as well as the absorption of over €65 billion from European funds between 2025 and 2028. In addition to Cohesion Policy, the PNRR represents another target, specifying that by the end of 2028, not only will the planned reforms and investments be implemented, but 100% of the total allocation of €28.5 billion will be absorbed, just as 30% of the funds allocated to the Social Climate Fund will be used by the end of 2028. The new post-2027 Multiannual Financial Framework is another important objective for the PSD, with the government program defining the issues of interest to Romania that will be promoted in the negotiations for the New Framework: maintaining the principle of shared management in cohesion policy; introducing specific allocations for Member States with underdeveloped transport and basic infrastructure (water and wastewater); setting up a special fund to directly finance rural areas in order to ensure minimum living standards; support for large industrial companies to obtain European funding; simplification of the rules for granting state aid; simplification of public procurement rules and professionalization in the field of public procurement; extension of the implementation period of the Recovery and Resilience Facility for the full use of the allocated funds.

Externally, the promotion of Romania's interests within the EU is not limited to those relating to the new post-2027 Multiannual Financial Framework, with defense and foreign policy also reflecting Romania's firm anchoring in the Euro-Atlantic area. In terms of defense, the aim is to increase Romania's strategic role within NATO and the EU (through participation in NATO and EU operations and missions; fulfilling the obligations arising from NATO and EU membership to ensure the capabilities necessary to achieve a high level of preparedness; participating in EU defense initiatives and the NATO defense planning and security investment process; intensifying bilateral and regional cooperation in the field of defense; managing migration challenges and border security). Regarding foreign policy, a

strong Romania in the EU is the first direction addressed, the second focusing on increasing Romania's role within NATO. From the PSD's perspective, a strong Romania in the EU means: active involvement in EU-level efforts to ensure a sustainable economic recovery, including through the use of EU financial mechanisms and instruments, and, in parallel with the dual transition - green and digital, by promoting solutions that facilitate the continuation of the convergence process within the Union; strengthening expertise in European affairs; strengthening the capacity of national institutions to analyze ex-ante and ex-post the impact of European legislation at the national level, as well as strengthening the process of timely and consistent transposition of European directives. Increasing Romania's role in NATO, strengthening the Strategic Partnership with the US, supporting the Republic of Moldova in its consolidation efforts, and Romania's accession to the OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) in 2026 are priority foreign policy issues for the PSD. The results of the parliamentary elections on December 1, 2024, placed the PSD in first place in the voting preferences of Romanians, both in the Senate (22.30%) and in the Chamber of Deputies (21.96%).

A comparison of the PSD's 2025–2028 governing program with the political priorities of the S&D group has identified several important common themes: full European integration of member states into the EU (the PSD supports Romania's accession to the Schengen Area and the Eurozone, and the S&D Group supporting deeper European integration and strengthening the EU); social policies and reducing inequalities (the PSD focuses on reducing social and economic gaps with the EU average, and the S&D Group promotes a strengthened European Pillar of Social Rights, with equal access to services and social protection); labor policies and worker protection (the PSD supports labor mobility in the EU, with equal treatment for Romanians, while the S&D group calls for equal rights for all workers and decent working conditions); economic policies and European funds (the PSD focuses on the absorption of European funds, the common agricultural policy, and cohesion policy, while the S&D Group supports cohesion funds and European public investment for equitable development); climate and energy policies (the PSD supports the European Green Deal, but with attention to national interests—energy mix, and the S&D Group promotes a just green transition, with job protection and support for vulnerable communities); security and defense policies (the PSD supports cooperation with NATO and the EU, participating in the PSAC, while the S&D Group calls for a more united EU in the field of security, capable of responding to external crises). We therefore note that there is strong alignment between the PSD and the European S&D family on: European integration, social policies, workers' rights, economic cohesion and European funds, a just green transition, and cooperation on security and defense.

The National Liberal Party (PNL). The National Liberal Party (PNL) is a historic political party, founded on May 24, 1875, and reestablished after the 1989 Revolution, with a center-right orientation. In the 35 years since the Revolution, PNL has managed to bring under its banner not only groups claiming to be liberal, but, after 2001, it has also managed to consolidate its position by absorbing other parties considered ideologically compatible. For PNL, Romania's commitments regarding its membership in the EU and NATO, as well as its strategic partnership with the US, represent the main directions of its foreign policy. As regards its position on the EU, PNL supports the promotion of a united and strong Europe, based on the values of democracy, respect for human rights and freedoms, and the rule of law, by integrating national values and traditions with those of Western modernity¹².

After 1989, PNL participated in the governing coalition between 1996 and 2000 as part of the Democratic Convention (CDR), after which, in 2003, it became part of the Justice and Truth Alliance

¹² See <https://pnl.ro/principii-si-valori/>.

(Alianța DA PNL-PD) – which was in government between 2004 and 2007. Between 2012 and 2014 it was part of the government within the Social Liberal Union (USL). From 2019 to the present, PNL has governed twice as a minority government (2019–2020, 2021) and as part of the National Coalition for Romania (between 2020–2021, 2021–2024). The parliamentary elections held after 1989 placed PNL fourth in the voting options between 2000 and 2004, third twice (1990–1992, 2008–2012), second four times (1992–1996 as part of the CDR, 2004–2008 as part of the DA Alliance, 2016–2020, 2020–2024) and in first place twice (1996–2000 as part of the CDR, 2012–2016 as part of the USL).

In the European Parliament, following the merger with PDL on November 17, 2014, PNL became a member of the European People's Party (EPP) group, thus leaving the ALDE (Alliance of Liberals and Democrats for Europe) group. During the four rounds of elections, until the 2024 elections, PNL came in first place, obtaining the highest number of votes in the 2019 elections, second place in the 2014 elections, with PNL MEPs becoming members of the EPP group in both elections, while in the 2009 and 2007 elections it only came third, with PNL MEPs becoming members of the ALDE group, the European political family to which the PNL belonged before its merger with the PDL.

In the European Parliament elections on June 9, 2024, as a result of the joint candidacy with the PSD, on the lists of the PSD-PNL Alliance, and with a joint program - presented under the slogan "We stand with Romania" - the Alliance obtained 48.55% of the votes of Romanian citizens, resulting in 19 seats, with the PNL thus sending eight MEPs to Brussels. In the local elections, held concurrently with the European elections, the PNL obtained 29.07% of the votes for mayors (second place, after the PSD), namely 1,132 seats, and for county councils – the percentage obtained was 11 seats out of 41 (second place, after the PSD).

The eight MEPs from the PNL became, after the June 2024 elections, members of the European People's Party (EPP) group, the largest group in the European Parliament and, after the European elections of June 6-9, 2024, a group which, in the 2024-2029 term, brings together 188 MEPs from the political parties of the member states. For the 2024 European elections, the EPP group launched at the Congress in Bucharest on March 6-7, 2024, the "EPP Manifesto 2024" - entitled "Our Europe, a safe and good home for people"¹³. The manifesto reiterates the EPP Group's support for a democratic Europe that upholds its fundamental values, both within and beyond its borders, and which, at the same time, seeks to regain "the trust of those who feel unheard or left behind". A Europe that "preserves its democracy, traditions, cultural richness, and diversity". The EPP's commitment to defending European values and democracy involves measures to ensure the protection of the rule of law, freedom of the press, and fundamental rights; the fight against disinformation and external interference; and the strengthening of European identity through education and cultural exchanges. A secure and strong Europe (by strengthening European defense, in close cooperation with NATO; strong support for Ukraine and resistance to Russian aggression; strengthening external borders and combating illegal migration); economic prosperity and competitiveness (by promoting a globally competitive European economy; supporting SMEs, innovation, and investment in infrastructure; reducing bureaucracy and creating a business-friendly environment); balanced green transition (by supporting climate goals, but with an emphasis on pragmatism and protecting jobs; promoting clean energy, including nuclear energy and gas as transition solutions; support for farmers and food security); a digital and innovative Europe (by investing in artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructure; or by creating a competitive and secure digital single market); responsible social policies (by promoting equal opportunities and mobility within the EU; supporting family and demographic

¹³ Available at: https://www.epp.eu/files/uploads/2024/03/Manifesto_2024.pdf.

policies; investing in education, training, and health); EU as a global actor (by creating a more united and influential Union in the world; expanding the EU to the Western Balkans, Ukraine, Moldova, and Georgia, conditional on reforms; a foreign policy based on strategic partnerships and fair trade), represent the guidelines for the initiatives that the EPP will support in the new term of the European Parliament, 2024-2029. As far as Romania is concerned, the Manifesto also includes a special mention, awaited by Romanian politicians at the Congress in Bucharest, regarding the European People's Party's commitment to Romania's accession, alongside Bulgaria, to the Schengen Area, including land borders.

PNL's 2025-2028 governing program¹⁴, under the motto "A secure and prosperous Romania," contains in its 237 pages references to EU policies and their harmonization with national policies, as well as to Romania's place in the EU. It mentions support for accelerating the process of accession to the Schengen Area and the Eurozone, as well as increasing economic convergence with EU states, as steps aimed at strengthening Romania's integration into the EU. With regard to European policies, the Program mentions economic and cohesion policies (through the use of European funds for regional development, support for cohesion policy and the common agricultural policy, or the promotion of investment through European funds and the PNRR); security and defense policies (strengthening Romania's membership in European security structures, increasing cooperation with NATO and the EU for common defense); European climate and energy policies (supporting the European Green Deal and the transition to renewable energy; creating a balanced energy mix in line with EU climate objectives); social and labor policies (promoting equal opportunities and labor mobility within the EU, supporting young people through European educational programs - e.g., Erasmus+); policies on digitization and innovation (alignment with the EU's digital strategy; investments in digital infrastructure and artificial intelligence). Extremely important are the references to strengthening Romania's role in the EU by promoting an active foreign policy, so that Romania can be an "influential member state" in the EU, but also by increasing its participation in European decisions. Thus, PNL wishes to contribute to building a "cohesive, strong, secure, and competitive" Europe. Strengthening Romania's strategic position in NATO and its partnership with the US, joining the OECD, supporting the European path of the Republic of Moldova, and consolidating Romania's role as a pillar of stability in the Southeast European region are also priority objectives that PNL pursues externally. The results of the parliamentary elections on December 1, 2024, placed PNL in second place in the voting options, both in the Senate (14.28%) and in the Chamber of Deputies (13.20%).

A comparison of PNL's 2025–2028 governing program with EPP's 2024 manifesto has identified some common themes: a competitive economy and support for SMEs (PNL is considering measures to reduce bureaucracy, support small and medium-sized enterprises, improve access to finance, and ensure predictable fiscal policies); EPP group is concerned with reducing the administrative burden – based on the "one in, two out" principle, supports the idea of a European commissioner dedicated to SMEs, the promotion of a European industrial policy and a "Made in Europe 2030" initiative); Green transition and energy (the PNL supports the continuation of the European Green Deal, investment in renewable energy, support for hydrogen, energy security, and energy market integration. the EPP group supports the goal of achieving climate neutrality by 2050, neutral technology policies – including nuclear and gas, investment in energy infrastructure and hydrogen), agriculture and food security (the PNL supports helping farmers, adapting the CAP to Romanian conditions, investment in irrigation and climate resilience; the EPP group advocates for the strong defense of farmers, a more balanced CAP adapted to climate and demographic challenges, and the promotion of precision agriculture and

¹⁴ Available at <https://campanii.pnl.ro/2024/?path=/prioritati>.

biotechnologies); social policies and demography (the PNL supports family support, active demographic policies, combating poverty, and investments in education and health; the EPP group aims to strengthen the family as the core of society, policies for young people and combating unemployment, an expanded Erasmus+, and a strategy for demography); the rule of law and European values (the PNL has expressed its commitment to strengthening the rule of law, the independence of the judiciary, and respect for European values; the EPP group supports the defense of the rule of law, the conditionality mechanism for EU funds, combating disinformation, and protecting the press); defense and security (the PNL supports relations with NATO, investment in defense, strengthening cybersecurity, and providing support to Ukraine; the EPP group supports cooperation with NATO, a European Defense Union, a European fund for external military interventions, and firm support for Ukraine); EU enlargement and the Eastern Neighborhood (the PNL supports EU enlargement towards the Western Balkans, Ukraine, Moldova and Georgia; the EPP group supports enlargement based on clear criteria – the Copenhagen criteria, support for Ukraine, Moldova and the Western Balkans). Therefore, we note that the PNL and the EPP group are aligned on the broad directions: competitive economy, SME support, realistic green transition, strategic agriculture, defense and NATO, rule of law, EU enlargement. The differences are more at the level of detail, with the PNL placing greater emphasis on Romania's needs (irrigation, access to EU funds, national infrastructure), while the EPP group focuses on the transnational vision (common European policies, institutional mechanisms, and integrated markets).

Save Romania Union (USR). The Save Romania Union (USR), a party founded in 2016, defines itself as a new, anti-establishment, center-right party¹⁵. For USR, membership in the EU and NATO are important achievements for Romania that must be consolidated, just as it considers that Romania's strategic development in line with the opportunities offered by EU membership is necessary. Between 2016 and 2020, USR was the third largest political party in the Romanian Parliament, occupying the same position between 2020 and 2024 as part of the USR-PLUS Alliance, and participated in the governing coalition between December 2020 and August 2021, alongside PNL and UDMR.

On December 18, 2023, the Save Romania Union (USR), the People's Movement Party (PMP), and the Right Force (FD) officially launched a center-right alliance called the United Right Alliance (ADU). In this configuration, they participated in the European and local elections in June 2024, when they obtained 8.71% of the vote and three seats in the European Parliament, and 6.28% in the mayoral elections (28 seats), but failed to win any seats for county council presidents.

For the European elections on June 9, 2024, the United Right Alliance (ADU) came up with a program entitled "The United Right's Commitment to a Modern Romania"¹⁶. The twelve points of the program focused on: Romania's accession to the Schengen Area and the Eurozone; continuing the fight against corruption and eliminating political privileges; democracy and the rule of law (defending the EU from illiberal tendencies and supporting democracy in Romania against the negative influences of the PSD-PNL Coalition); aligning the health and education systems with European standards, with more responsibilities for the EU in these areas; efficient use of EU funds (modernization of Romania through the PNRR and the cohesion fund, efficient spending of EU funds), agriculture (financing family farms at European level and combating the black market that destabilizes the agricultural sector), support for the Republic of Moldova (supporting Moldova's accession to the EU and reuniting Romanians under the umbrella of the EU); Romania's role in the EU (taking an active role in the institutional reform of

¹⁵ See <https://usr.ro/centru-dreapta-modern/>.

¹⁶ See <https://usr.ro/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Angajamentul-Dreptei-Unite-pentru-Romania-Moderna.pdf>.

the EU); the rights of Romanian workers (ensuring decent incomes and pensions for Romanians in Europe through active policies for retraining and organizing the workforce); a clean environment and energy (transition to renewable energy sources, maintaining balance and national specificity); European defense (integration of European armies into NATO and support for Ukraine to respond to geopolitical challenges). The program also details, for each of the twelve points, the expectations that ADU has of its future MEPs, namely: to be negotiators, defenders of Romanians in the EU, promoters of European integration and reform, and to be directly connected to communities, explaining the advantages and using EU resources in the national interest.

For the parliamentary elections on December 1, 2024, USR ran on its own lists (ADU having been dissolved on September 6, 2024), managing to obtain a score of 12.26% in the Senate and 12.40% in the Chamber of Deputies. USR's governing program, entitled "A Romania for all, not just for some"¹⁷: Romania's integration into the Schengen Area and the Eurozone; the rule of law and European values (strengthening the independence of the judiciary and the rule of law as the foundation of EU membership, but also implementing the CVM and GRECO recommendations); European funds and development (increasing the absorption rate of European funds; simplifying administrative procedures for the use of European resources; using funds for regional development and infrastructure); climate and energy policies (supporting the objectives of the European Green Deal; accelerating the transition to renewable energy and reducing dependence on fossil fuels; promoting energy efficiency); digital policies and innovation (active participation in the EU's digital strategy; investment in technology, digital infrastructure, and cybersecurity; promoting innovation and the digital economy); European foreign and security policies (strengthening the partnership with NATO and the EU for common defense; participation in EU security initiatives; support for Ukraine and the Republic of Moldova on their European path); European social and education policies (expanding access to programs such as Erasmus+; promoting youth mobility and academic exchanges; reducing social gaps through European inclusion policies).

USR, a member of the Renew Europe Group in the European Parliament (a group that ranked fourth among the eight political groups of the tenth legislature in the 2024 European elections, with 77 MEPs), has proven, after comparing its governing program with the future priorities of the Renew Europe Group, that they are almost perfectly aligned in terms of pro-Europeanism, the rule of law, common security, support for Ukraine, the Green Deal, digitization, SMEs, and managed migration..

The **Hungarian Democratic Union of Romania (UDMR)**. The Hungarian Democratic Union of Romania (UDMR), founded on December 25, 1989, immediately after the fall of communism in Romania, has as its main purpose the public representation of the interests of the Hungarian community in Romania (which is 6.05% of the population, according to the official results of the 2022 census). The two main objectives that the party has pursued since its inception have been: the creation of the rule of law and its institutions, and the integration of Romania into the Euro-Atlantic community¹⁸.

Since the first elections were held, the UDMR has been represented in both the Romanian Parliament (from 1990 to the present) and the European Parliament (from 2007 to the present). Thus, over the past 35 years, it has repeatedly experienced being both an opposition party (the first such experience took place between 1990 and 1996) and a government partner (the first such experience took place between 2000 and 2004, with the PDSR), as well as a ruling party (the first such experience

¹⁷ Available at: <https://usr.ro/program-guvernare-2024/>.

¹⁸ Available at: <https://udmr.ro/page/despre-noi>.

took place between 1996 and 2000, alongside the CDR and USD), sometimes with partners of a different ideological persuasion.

UDMR's candidacy for the European Parliament elections on June 9, 2024, was based on a twelve-point electoral program under the slogan "We win together"¹⁹, in which the objectives that UDMR will promote in the new term of the European Parliament are presented in a format that includes, on the one hand, observations, criticisms, directed at the EU, and UDMR's proposal, on the other hand: support for EU legislation on the protection of minorities; Romania to receive the EU funds allocated to it; the EU to contribute to the creation of jobs for young people in the country, not abroad; the implementation of the European minimum wage in Romania; the decision-making process in migration management to remain within the competence of the Member States; the new migration pact has not eliminated the mandatory quota system, but has merely disguised it in the form of financial payments; the EU should provide more support to Romanian farmers and local products, instead of supporting Ukrainian grain exports; there should be more support for small and medium-sized enterprises; bureaucracy in Brussels should be reduced; the ecological transition should be fair, not forced; the EU should adapt its ambitious climate targets to the economic potential and social tolerance of Member States. the EU should revise the Habitats Directive and remove the brown bear from its list of strictly protected species. Stronger action should be taken against extremism. A Europe that is relevant on the world stage should be built. The results of the June 9 vote placed UDMR in fourth place in terms of the number of votes obtained, with a percentage of 6.48%. The two MEP seats (only in the 2009 elections did UDMR have three MEPs) obtained by UDMR will be added to the EPP Group, the UDMR being the first Romanian party to join this political group after the 1989 Revolution.

In its 2025–2028 Government Program²⁰, UDMR emphasizes that Romania must remain firmly anchored in the EU and NATO, as these are fundamental guarantees of security and development, but stresses the need for Romania to be an active player, not a passive beneficiary, within the EU cooperation framework, and to participate actively in the future of the EU, including institutional reforms. The main European policy themes found in UDMR's governing program are: full integration into the EU (through accession to the Schengen Area and adoption of the euro); economic policies and European funds (with a view to the efficient absorption of European funds - PNRR, structural funds, CAP; reducing regional disparities through the coherent use of cohesion funds; connecting the Romanian economy to the single market through investment in infrastructure and digitization); social policies and the protection of Romanian workers (support for the implementation of the European Pillar of Social Rights; defending the rights of Romanians in the diaspora – equal treatment, social protection, mutually recognized pensions; strengthening policies for youth, education and mobility – Erasmus+); environmental and energy policies (support for the green transition, but at a balanced pace, adapted to Romania's specific circumstances; investment in renewable energy, but also maintaining an energy mix that ensures energy security; focus on sustainable development in rural areas and support for farmers under the CAP); security and foreign policies (UDMR supports the strengthening of the EU's Common Security and Defense Policy, in complementarity with NATO; firm support for Ukraine and the Republic of Moldova, Moldova's integration into the EU; Romania's involvement in the neighborhood policy and in the EU's enlargement towards the Western Balkans); and last but not least, EU reform (UDMR supports a more democratic and transparent Union, in which decisions are closer to citizens; but also a balanced position in the EU, through openness to deeper integration, while

¹⁹ Available at: <https://9iunie.udmr.ro/>.

²⁰ Available at: <https://bunsimt.udmr.ro/>

respecting the sovereignty of Member States and the principle of subsidiarity). A comparison of the positions of UDMR and the EPP Group on current issues and European policies shows almost total alignment, with convergence on topics such as: full European integration, funds and cohesion, pragmatic green transition, agriculture, security, and EU reform, with the difference being that UDMR emphasizes Romania's needs (diaspora, irrigation, regional disparities), while the EPP formulates a transnational vision (European instruments, institutional mechanisms).

The 6.38% obtained in the Senate and 6.33% in the Chamber of Deputies gave UDMR a new presence in the Romanian Parliament, thus becoming a parliamentary party for the tenth time since 1990. In the local elections of June 9, 2024, the 4.32% obtained in the mayoral elections brought the UDMR a total of 200 seats at the national level, while the 6.04% obtained in the elections for county council presidents brought the UDMR a total of four seats.

A pro-European coalition and government. On June 23, 2025, the PSD, PNL, USR, UDMR, and the Parliamentary Group of National Minorities in the Chamber of Deputies signed an agreement on the formation of a pro-Western political coalition government for the period 2025-2028²¹. The agreement stipulates, as the name of the coalition suggests, that Romania's pro-European and Euro-Atlantic course are fundamental elements of the programs and policies promoted by the coalition and its representatives. On the same day, the government negotiated within the coalition and led by Ilie Bolojan received a vote of confidence from Parliament with 301 votes "for" (68 more votes than it needed) and 9 votes "against," while the AUR parliamentarians left the chamber. The prime minister and members of the government then took the oath of office at the Cotroceni Palace in the presence of President Nicușor Dan.

The Coalition's 2025-2028 Government Program²² firmly states that Romania remains firmly anchored in the EU and NATO, with the Government committing to promoting European values: democracy, the rule of law, and fundamental rights. Full integration into the EU is a strategic priority—joining the Schengen Area—and a medium-term political and economic goal—adopting the euro—as well as strengthening Romania's role as an active and involved member state. As regards national and European public policy objectives, the Government Program includes: economic policies and European funds (the aim is to maximize the absorption of European funds - PNRR, structural funds, sectoral programs; connecting national investments to EU strategies - green transition, digitization, competitiveness; but also reducing development gaps compared to the EU average); social and labor policies (promoting the European Pillar of Social Rights; protecting the rights of Romanians working in other EU countries; combating social exclusion through programs supported by European funds); environmental policies and the green transition (implementing the European Green Deal, but adapted to Romania's interests; supporting investments in renewable energy, energy efficiency, and the circular economy; balancing climate goals with the need to protect economic competitiveness); security and foreign policies (Romania supports the strengthening of the Common Security and Defense Policy – CSDP; expresses its commitment to supporting Ukraine and the Republic of Moldova; but also involvement in EU policies on the Eastern Neighborhood and the Western Balkans). Regarding EU reform and Romania's position, the governing coalition's position is that Romania supports a more democratic, transparent, and efficient EU, advocates for a balance between deeper integration and respect for the sovereignty of member states, being involved in debates on the future of Europe.

²¹ Available at: <https://www.udmr.ro/upload/dokumentumok/ACORD%20POLITIC%20PSD-PNL-USR-UDMR-GMR%202025-06-23.pdf>.

²² Available at: https://www.gov.ro/fisiere/pagini_fisiere/25-06-24-11-11-52PROGRAM_DE_GVERNARE.pdf.

A comparative analysis of the 2025–2028 Coalition Government Program (Romania) with the Political Guidelines for the European Commission 2024–2029 highlighted several common themes, such as: European and Euro-Atlantic anchoring (the Coalition Program emphasizes Romania's membership in the EU and NATO, with clear objectives: strengthening the Schengen area, adopting the euro, active involvement in the EU – by contributing to the achievement of the objectives of the new Strategic Agenda 2024-2029 and promoting a strengthened Romanian presence in European institutions, including in leadership positions; the European Commission emphasizes European unity, strengthening the EU-NATO relationship, and Europe's role in the world); fundamental democratic values (the Romanian government affirms the promotion of democracy, the rule of law, and fundamental rights; the Commission's guidelines emphasize defending democracy, combating extremism, and protecting social fairness); economic policies and competitiveness (Romania wants to maximize the absorption of EU funds, connect investments to the green and digital transition, and reduce disparities; the Commission is pursuing a "Plan for sustainable prosperity and competitiveness", investments in innovation, digitization, clean energy, and reducing external dependencies); social policies and the labor market (Romania supports the implementation of the European Social Pillar, protecting Romanian workers in the EU, combating social exclusion; The Commission wants to strengthen the Social Pillar, education and skills - STEM, a "Skills Union"); green transition and environmental policies (Romania supports the implementation of the European Green Deal, adapted to national interests, and has expressed support for renewable energy and the circular economy; The Commission aims to implement the Pact for a clean industry, climate neutrality by 2050, investment in green technologies and renewable energy); security and defense (Romania supports the PSAC, the accession of Ukraine and the Republic of Moldova, involvement in the Eastern Neighborhood and the Western Balkans; The Commission aims to strengthen a Defense Union, increase investment in security, partnership with NATO, continued support for Ukraine, and EU enlargement to the East); reform and the future of the EU (Romania supports a more democratic, more efficient EU, but with respect for the sovereignty of states; The Commission: wants a "faster, simpler, more united" Union, ready for enlargement and structural reforms).

National and European issues in the electoral offers of the populist opposition

This section analyzes the electoral offers of the three populist political parties (AUR, SOS - Partidul SOS România, and POT), which passed the 5% electoral threshold to secure seats in the European and national legislatures and which, at the domestic level, provide strong opposition to the pro-European parties.

The **Alliance for the Union of Romanians (AUR)**. The Alliance for the Union of Romanians (AUR) is a young political party, founded in September 2019, which identifies itself as a conservative party, whose ideology is based on four values: family (traditional), nation, faith (Christian), and freedom (with certain limits)²³. AUR is the main national-populist party, as evidenced by the results it has achieved since the 2020 parliamentary elections when, from a party considered to have "come out of nowhere", which at the time did not attract the attention of either political analysts or the media, it managed to enter Parliament, occupying fourth place in both the Senate and the Chamber of Deputies. As subsequent analyses show, massive promotion on Facebook and in Romanian communities in the diaspora contributed to the rapid success of AUR.

²³ Available at: <https://partidulaur.ro/statut/>.

Participating for the first time in the European elections on June 9, 2024, resulted in another success, with AUR (Alliance for the Union of Romanians, Romanian National Conservative Party, Romanians for Romania Party) managing to enter the European Parliament with 14.93% of the vote, thus sending six MEPs to Brussels. AUR's eleven-point program was structured around several fundamental principles and priority objectives. Thus, AUR supports five important aspects in its relationship with the EU: benefits for Romania (the relationship with the EU must bring benefits to Romania and its citizens); Romania is a full member of the EU and supports a strong Europe that responds to the needs of all citizens); respect for national identity and sovereignty (AUR will only support a Europe that respects citizens, fundamental freedoms, Christian identity, and the family as the pillar of society); democracy and freedom (AUR supports real democracy, freedom, and equality within the EU, as well as the promotion of peace); and union with the Republic of Moldova (supporting the accession of the Republic of Moldova to the EU, with the freely consented union of the two Romanian states as a concrete objective). These priority areas are therefore based on three fundamental principles: Romania's sovereignty (Romania must be a sovereign state that contributes to European development and stability); cooperation and cohesion (promoting cohesion within the EU and reducing economic disparities between Member States); the defense of Romanians' rights (guaranteeing the rights of all Romanians within and outside the EU). Therefore, in its relationship with the EU, the AUR advocates for reducing bureaucracy and social assistance, but also for access to EU funds; education (with an emphasis on investing in the future of young people); health services (improving services for Romanians); agriculture and rural development (supporting agriculture and rural areas); culture and identity (promoting Romanian culture and identity); the development of Romanian companies (supporting Romanian entrepreneurship); foreign relations (defending Romania's interests abroad); tourism (developing tourism); and the environment and energy (by promoting sustainability and energy independence).

The six Romanian MEPs have become members of the European Conservatives and Reformists Group (ECR), a political group established in 2009 that defines itself as a center-right group. For the 2024-2029 term of the European Parliament²⁴, ECR has set itself several objectives relating to the EU and its policies under the motto "Back to common sense": national sovereignty and institutional reform (opposition to a "European superstate" and the centralization of power in Brussels; defense of subsidiarity and existing treaties, decisions must be taken as close as possible to citizens; protection of national identities and democracies); defense and security (the EU must prioritize security; strengthening the European defense industry and support for joint research and procurement; strong support for Ukraine, tougher sanctions against Russia, support for Moldova and Georgia; close cooperation with NATO, maintaining NATO as the main guarantor of European security); migration and border security (a firm approach to illegal migration; proposal for external platforms for processing asylum applications; strengthening of Frontex and Europol; combating human trafficking and abuses in the asylum system); agriculture and fisheries (Common Agricultural Policy - CAP less bureaucratic and tailored to farmers; protecting the competitiveness of European farmers, promoting innovation; national forest management, opposition to the expansion of the Commission's powers; reform of the Common Fisheries Policy, support for sustainable fishing and partnerships with third countries); industry, energy and the Green Deal (criticism of "ecological extremism"; desire to revise the Green Deal to avoid negative effects on the economy and jobs; opposition to the ban on internal combustion engines from 2035; support for technology-neutral energy transition - including nuclear, gas,

²⁴ Available at: https://ecrgroup.eu/files/EN_ECR-Priorities_2024-2029.pdf.

geothermal; priority for energy security and strategic infrastructure); economy and single market (reducing bureaucracy and promoting the "Think Small First" principle for SMEs; rigorous impact assessments before new regulations; breaking down a level playing field in the single market, combating unfair subsidies; reforming the services market and standards to encourage innovation); budget and taxation (support for a more efficient, results-based EU budget; categorical opposition to the introduction of EU-wide taxes; upholding the fiscal sovereignty of Member States); fundamental rights and freedoms (defending freedom of expression and opposing online censorship; support for internet anonymity and parental control, not government surveillance; combating anti-Semitism and all forms of extremism); foreign policy and enlargement (support for EU enlargement - Western Balkans, Ukraine, Moldova, but based on the Copenhagen criteria; strengthening relations with the UK, India, the US, NATO). The 2024 European elections placed the CRE Group in fourth place, after the EPP, S&D, and PFE, with 78 MEPs.

For the parliamentary elections on December 1, 2024, AUR came up with a government program entitled "Simion's Plan" and with the motto "Rebuilding Romania"²⁵. Chapter I of the fifteen chapters of the Program, detailed in 287 pages, is entitled "Romanians." From the outset, AUR states that "Romanians are worthy in Europe and in the world," but emphasizes that "this dignity must be affirmed." Thus, in an imperative tone, the party states that it will counteract, through all legal and institutional instruments, agreements and directives that may affect the interests of Romania and Romanians, because "Romanians are equal to other citizens of EU states." In this regard, it declares that AUR will renegotiate treaties, membership of the Schengen area, the Green Deal, and the PNRR, on the principle of equal rights, obligations, and benefits.

A special message is aimed at Romanians outside Romania, with AUR declaring that they do not represent a "second-class Romania". For this reason, it announces that it will protect and promote the interests of historical Romanian communities and Romanians in the diaspora; that the rule of representation must be the same for all Romanians, inside and outside the country, but also that Romania will no longer be an exporter of cheap labor. It uses the same imperative language with regard to AUR's position on the EU (AUR is a pro-European party; the Euro-Atlantic option is strategic and irrevocable; it rejects the tendency to centralize decision-making at the EU level) and Romania's place in the EU (the national interest will be the central axis of Romania's foreign policy; it will ensure, through negotiations, that the treaties in force are respected by European and Euro-Atlantic partners, but also regarding the recognition of Romania's role as an ally and member state with equal rights; it will counteract, through all legal and institutional instruments, agreements and directives that may affect the interests of Romania and Romanians; and it will aim to raise the standard of living in our country to the EU average over the next decade).

And, as mentioned in AUR's party statute, the idea of reunification with the Republic of Moldova is reiterated. Based on these statements, it appears that AUR takes a position both on the nature of the relationship between national sovereignty and the EU (by supporting the limitation of the influence of European institutions on internal decisions; opposition to the federalization of the EU; or promoting a Europe of nations based on cooperation, not centralization), as well as on the integration process and EU treaties (by expressing its intention to reevaluate European treaties where they diminish Romania's sovereignty, or opposing the expansion of Brussels' powers in areas considered national sovereignty). With regard to European issues and policies, we note that AUR's position is nuanced and sovereigntist, whether we are referring to economic policies and European

²⁵ Available at: https://programaur.ro/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/CARTEA-AUR_nou.pdf.

funds (use of European funds only to the extent that they respect Romania's interests; criticism of the PNRR and the conditions imposed by the EU); EU social and labor policies (defending the rights of Romanians working abroad; demanding equal treatment for Romanian citizens in EU countries); energy and climate policies (reservations about the objectives of the European Green Deal, considered burdensome for Romania; promotion of a national energy mix adapted to Romania's interests); or foreign and security policy (support for European security cooperation, but on condition that national sovereignty is respected; reservations about EU initiatives that would limit Romania's control over its own foreign policy).

The results of the 2024 parliamentary elections placed the AUR party second in the voting preferences of Romanians, with 18.30% of the vote in the Senate and 18.01% in the Chamber of Deputies. This was after it won only 30 mayoral seats (6.27%) and no county council president seats in the local elections on June 9, 2024.

A comparison of the AUR party's 2025-2028 governing program with ECR's 2024-2029 priorities has identified several common directions and themes: national sovereignty and subsidiarity (AUR criticizes the federalization of the EU and calls for a "Europe of nations"; the ECR Group rejects the idea of a "European superstate" and defends subsidiarity and national democracies); migration policies (AUR opposes refugee quotas and EU policies on the redistribution of migrants; the ECR Group calls for firm measures against illegal migration, external asylum processing, border reinforcement, and conditional cooperation); energy policies and the Green Deal (AUR has major reservations about the European Green Deal and insists on an energy mix tailored to Romania's interests; the ECR Group criticizes "ecological extremism" and calls for a review of the Green Deal); agriculture and farmers (AUR supports the protection of Romanian farmers, reducing dependence on imports, adapting the CAP to national interests; the ECR Group calls for simplification of the CAP, support for farmers, less bureaucracy, precision farming); economic policies (AUR accepts the use of EU funds only if they respect Romania's interests, expresses opposition to conditionality, supports the national economy; The ECR Group advocates reducing bureaucracy, supporting SMEs, and a fair single market); foreign policy and enlargement (AUR has reservations about expanding Brussels' powers, but expresses support for its eastern neighbors - Moldova; The ECR Group expresses its support for EU enlargement - Ukraine, Moldova, the Balkans, but on strict criteria, as well as privileged relations with the UK and NATO. This comparison shows that the AUR and the ECR Group share a sovereigntist vision, critical of the federalization of the EU, both emphasizing the defense of national interests, the differences between them being one of intensity and discourse, with the ECR Group taking a more pragmatic approach, oriented towards reform and adjustment of the EU, while AUR has a more radical discourse, strongly anti-centralization and critical of Brussels..

SOS Romania Party (SOS). The SOS Romania Party is a nationalist, conservative, right-wing populist, and Eurosceptic party that was founded in November 2021, but became known on the Romanian political scene in May 2022 after Senator Diana Șoșoacă, elected in 2020 on the AUR lists, joined the party and became its leader. The SOS Romania party is considered to be more radical than AUR. Șoșoacă has called for Romania's withdrawal from the EU and criticized NATO, while the party's website states that it opposes "the dictatorships of Russia and China" and supports Romania's integration into the EU. The party is also irredentist, demanding that Ukraine, through a bill submitted by Senator Diana Șoșoacă, return to Romania the territories annexed by the Soviet Union in 1940, which are now part of Ukraine, namely Northern Bukovina, Herța, Bugeac (Cahul, Bolgrad, Ismail), historic Maramureș, and Serpent Island. In response to Diana Șoșoacă's initiative, the Ukrainian

Ministry of Foreign Affairs stated that it would impose sanctions against Diana Șoșoacă as a person who poses a threat to Ukraine's national security.

For the European Parliament elections on June 9, 2024, the SOS Romania Party has developed a program²⁶ that comprises four chapters and expresses a nationalist, Eurosceptic, and conservative direction: "measures for Romanians" (supporting the use of wood and coal for energy; defending Romanian farmers against double standards for products; simplifying tax rules and reducing taxes and duties; reducing the retirement age to 60; maintaining the leu as the national currency); the rights and freedoms of Romanians (seeking compensation from the European Commission for the side effects of Covid vaccines; challenging the restrictions and health policies imposed by the EU - including Ursula von der Leyen; neutrality for Romania, and rejection of participation in wars and sanctions; support for Romanians in the diaspora and for their protection in the EU; opposition to illegal immigration and mandatory relocation quotas; rejection of "ideological propaganda", including LGBT); peace and prosperity (restoring regional cooperation - e.g. the Balkans, to defend sovereignty; withdrawal of foreign troops and NATO/EU bases from Romanian territory; recovery of European funds for infrastructure projects - motorways, the Danube-Bucharest Canal, the Port of Constanța; limiting imports of agricultural products to protect domestic production; stopping deforestation and imports of wood/wood products; reindustrializing Romania and supporting domestic production; developing agriculture through subsidies and reducing bureaucracy; stopping drug and human trafficking; opposition to EU policies on migration and climate change); tradition and faith (protecting traditional values and national identity; opposition to globalism and progressive ideologies - LGBT, multiculturalism; supporting the traditional family and the Orthodox faith as pillars of society). The results of the European Parliament elections gave the SOS Romania Party 5.03% of the total number of votes, which allowed it, from its first candidacy, to enter the European Parliament with two MEPs, unaffiliated.

In the governing program of the SOS Romania Party²⁷ for the parliamentary elections on December 1, 2024, the official direction proposed is full and dignified accession to the EU and NATO, through the modernization of Romania according to European standards. Thus, Romania must meet the standards necessary for "acceptance as a full member of the community of developed states," with the party supporting the continuation of reforms for the rule of law, democracy, and a functional market economy as part of the integration process. In terms of European policies, the SOS Romania Party's program focused on: sustainable development and European standards (Romania's economic and social development must be aligned with the principles of sustainable development promoted at European level; education and health are considered areas that must be brought up to European standards; fiscal policy, the labor market, and social protection must be adapted to EU practices and standards); economic policies and convergence with Europe (Romania must eliminate economic imbalances and accelerate restructuring in order to reduce the gap with other Member States; the social market economy is seen as the European model to follow, based on dynamic and competitive private ownership; ee promotes the development of the middle class and domestic capital as the foundation of European economic integration); agriculture and property (property reform and agricultural modernization are presented as essential for achieving EU standards; the aim is to create modern and prosperous farms that are compatible with European agricultural policy); environmental policies (the importance of alignment with European environmental protection policies is emphasized;

²⁶ Available at: <https://sosro.ro/programul-partidului-s-o-s-romania-alegerile-pentru-parlamentul-european/>.

²⁷ Available at: <https://sosro.ro/programul-de-guvernare-al-partidului-s-o-s-romania/>.

Romania must learn to live "within ecological limits" in order to protect future generations, in the spirit of the European Green Deal); justice and the rule of law (consolidating the rule of law is seen as a prerequisite for European integration; promoting a unified, impartial justice system aligned with EU standards, with an emphasis on combating corruption and ensuring the independence of magistrates); foreign policy and Romania's role in the EU (Romania must clearly align itself with democratic states governed by the rule of law, not with "Russian and Chinese dictatorships"; advocates for active involvement in reforming the European integration process; Romania must have a respected position and an active role in European decision-making). The results of the parliamentary elections on December 1, 2024, gave the SOS Romania Party parliamentary status, with the party obtaining 7.76% of the vote in the Senate and 7.36% in the Chamber of Deputies. Unlike the parliamentary elections, the local elections, with the percentages obtained by the party - 0.97% for the election of mayors and 2.93% for the election of county council presidents, did not bring the party any mayor or county council president mandates.

The Young People's Party (POT). The Young People's Party (POT) is a sovereigntist political party, founded in April 2023 by Anamaria Gavrilă, a former AUR deputy. The party supported Călin Georgescu's candidacy in the 2024 presidential elections and is considered a party with a sovereigntist, nationalist, Christian right-wing, conservative, and populist ideology; an anti-establishment party that declares itself a supporter of traditional and Christian values; but also a party that declares itself Eurosceptic, with anti-Western messages. The party did not field any candidates in the European elections on June 9, 2024, but it did participate in the local elections (where it obtained 0.08% of the vote and 18 mayoral seats, but no county council president seats), as well as in the parliamentary elections. For the parliamentary elections, POT presented voters with a program²⁸ that focused on a relatively narrow set of key areas: young people, family, entrepreneurs, justice, education, functional public institutions, health, the Romanian Army, European funds, energy, the diaspora, the declassification of Romania, the state as the best payer, and animal protection and welfare. European funds are one of the priority themes, indicating that POT recognizes the importance of the EU as a source of funding and support for development projects. The POT program also emphasizes the need for the state to be a good and responsible payer, which may include the efficient and rapid use and absorption of European funds. Thus, the POT's position is that clear measures must be taken to make the most of European funds to combat corruption, simplify bureaucracy, better prepare public authorities, and have accessible real-time management. The results of the parliamentary elections also brought POT into the Romanian Parliament, with the party obtaining 6.39% of the vote for the Senate and 6.46% for the Chamber of Deputies.

Conclusions

The year 2024 and the first half of 2025 were a complicated period for Romania, during which it had to face multiple challenges, both internally and at the European level, given that the perception of these challenges (political, security, economic, etc.) of Romanian public opinion and the vote that Romanian citizens were to cast would determine whether the country would continue on its pro-European path or not, in all types of elections held during this period – European, local, parliamentary, and presidential.

Around the time of the first elections – the European and local ones – Romanian citizens, in opinion polls conducted at European level (EB), expressed their confidence in the EU and its main

²⁸ Available at: <https://sieupot.ro/program-politic>.

institutions (the European Parliament, the European Council, European Commission), but also their distrust of domestic institutions and organizations (political parties, parliament, and government) and their dissatisfaction with the way democracy works in Romania. The results of the votes cast in these four categories of elections ultimately led to a victory for the pro-European forces, albeit a nuanced one, given that, in both the European Parliament and parliamentary elections, populist parties obtained significant percentages and seats in these legislative structures.

Therefore, an analysis of the electoral offers of the pro-European parties (PSD - Social Democratic Party, PNL - National Liberal Party, USR - Save Romania Union, UDMR - Hungarian Democratic Union of Romania), which in June 2025 formed Romania's new pro-European government, together with the national minorities group, for the 2025-2028 term, showed that these parties understand the obligations that come with EU membership (hypothesis 2) – by adhering to European values and supporting the EU's objectives, the directions of the European Council's Strategic Agenda and the priorities of the European Commission, as well as consistency with the ideology of the party and the ideological orientation of the political group to which they belong (hypothesis 1). Thus, we observe consistency among these parties both in terms of European integration, in the sense of Romania's full integration into the EU (accession to the Schengen Area and the Eurozone), and in terms of strengthening Romania's position in EU institutions, as well as firm support for European values. The approach to European policies, whether we refer to economy, European funds, climate and energy, digitization and innovation, social policies and education, security and defense, or foreign policy, despite some nuances related to an ideological approach to representing national and European interests, follows the medium-term directions set by the decisions of the leaders of the Member States and the European Commission.

The analysis of the electoral offers of the three populist parties (AUR - Alliance for the Union of Romanians, SOS - SOS Romania Party, and POT - Young People's Party) is nuanced, given that, of the three parties, only AUR is part of a political group in the European Parliament, while the two MEPs from the SOS Romania Party are unaffiliated at European level, and POT did not participate in the European Parliament elections. Thus, only with regard to AUR can we say that its electoral offer reflects the ideological orientation of the party and the political group to which it belongs (ECR) (hypothesis 1). As regards their position on the EU, its values and policies, and Romania's place in the EU, all three populist parties have a sovereigntist and Eurosceptic approach (invalidating hypothesis 2, but confirming hypothesis 3), whether we refer to the benefits of EU membership for Romania, national identity and sovereignty, democracy and fundamental freedoms, defense and security, migration and border security, agriculture and fisheries, industry, energy and the Green Deal, the economy and the single market, European funds, budget and taxation, foreign policy, and enlargement.

In conclusion, we observe a validation of hypotheses 1 and 2 in the electoral offers of the four pro-European parties, and a validation of hypotheses 1 and 3 in the electoral offers of the three populist parties. Therefore, given the pressure that the latter exert on traditional, pro-European parties represent a reality that the current pro-European governing coalition must face in the medium and long term and can only counteract by delivering concrete policy results that respond both to the challenges of today's world and to the socio-economic dissatisfaction and expectations of Romanian citizens.

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